

Equilibrium studies on binary and ternary complexes of palladium and cadmium with some nitrogen and oxygen donor ligands

Dilip Kumar, Anurag Vaish and Ram Nayan*

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad-244 001, India

E-mail : ramnayan_2003@yahoo.co.in Fax : 91-591-2440070

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The metal-ligand equilibrium reactions involving palladium(II), cadmium(II) and 1,2-dihydroxybenzene, 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulfonic acid, 8-amino-1-naphthol-3,6-disulfonic acid, *o*-aminophenol and 4,5-dihydroxybenzene-1,3-disulfonic acid have been studied in solution at 25° and at ionic strength of 0.10 M (KNO₃). Formation of the binary, ternary and hydroxo complex species has been inferred in solution and the corresponding equilibrium constants have been evaluated and discussed.

Complex formation reactions of the second row transition elements, particularly involving Pd^{II} ion are scarce¹. Comparatively more work has been reported on binary complexes of Cd^{II} with oxygen and nitrogen donors. In continuation of our studies on binary and ternary complexes of nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) with 1,2-dihydroxybenzene (ca), 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulfonic acid (nn) and 8-amino-1-naphthol-3,6-disulfonic acid (an)². We report here quantitative equilibrium reactions involving palladium(II) or cadmium(II) and ca, nn, an, 4,5-dihydroxybenzene-1,3-disulfonic acid (tr) and *o*-aminophenol (ap). The pH metric experimental measurements have been made at 25° and at an ionic strength of 0.10 M KNO₃.

Results and discussion

Proton-ligand dissociation constants: The proton-ligand dissociation constants corresponding to dissociation of the two protons from ca, nn or an (two phenolic groups of ca and one amino and one phenolic group of nn (monosodium

salt) or an (disodium salt) are reported in the recent publication². The equilibria corresponding to dissociation of protons from the two phenolic groups of tr (disodium salt) are evident from the titration curve (not presented here). The light pink colour of the ligand gradually turns light yellow (expected due to tr⁴⁻) from pH ~9.0. The $K_1^H = 10^{-7.58 \pm 0.04}$ and $K_2^H = 10^{-11.56 \pm 0.03}$ value for the two phenolic groups are comparable with the values earlier reported by Akalin and Ozer³. A large deviation in K_1^H value of tr from that of ca ($K_1^H = 10^{-9.38}$)² is due to electron-withdrawing effect of sulphonic acid groups. These groups reduce electron density on phenolic group at position-4. Two protons are liberated in steps from the protonated amino group and the phenolic group, respectively of ap system. There is no sharp colour change, but a gradual change from brown to yellow and then to yellowish-green has been noted. The brown, yellow and the yellowish-green colour may be expected due to existence of protonated, neutral and anionic ligand species, respectively. The evaluated $K_1^H = 10^{-4.12 \pm 0.04}$ and $K_2^H = 10^{-10.53 \pm 0.02}$ values are in agreement with literature value⁴. The K_2^H value in ap is higher than that in ca ($K_2^H = 10^{-11.58}$)⁵ or tr. It is because of the weaker electron donating property of the neutral *o*-substituted-NH₂ group in ap than the *o*-substituted oxygen anion (after dissociation of first phenolic hydrogen) in ca or tr.

Binary complexes: pH vs *a* curve for 1 : 1, Pd^{II}-ca mixture (Fig. omitted) indicates a weak inflection at *a* = 2.0. A colour change from reddish-brown to light yellow in reaction mixture is also observed at pH ~7.6. The yellow colour intensity gradually increases up to pH ~11.0 (*a* = 2.30). Thus, it is concluded that Pd(ca) and Pd(ca)(OH)⁻, both light yellow species, are formed in solution up to pH ~11.0. The colour of Cd^{II}-ca, 1 : 1 mixture also turns into a light yellow

low solution at pH ~7.5 ($a = 0.12$). The light yellow colour gradually changes to dark yellow at pH ~8.8 ($a = 1.85$). Beyond pH ~8.8 the mixture remains as a turbid solution. The titration curve indicates an inflection at $a = 2.0$ which is due to formation of Cd(ca) species. The colour changes in 1 : 1, Pd^{II}-ca mixture are comparable to those in 1 : 1 system. But, appearance of a light yellow colour (different from ligand colour-light green) and a steep inflection in pH vs a curve at $a = 2.0$ indicate formation of Pd(ca)₂²⁻ in solution. In Cd^{II} system also a gradual colour change in the pH range of complex formation, from light yellow to dark yellow is observed. A very strong inflection in the corresponding pH vs a curve at $a = 2.0$ (pH ~10.5) also supports the formation of yellow Cd(ca)₂²⁻ complex.

The colour intensity of 1 : 1, Pd^{II}-tr mixture gradually changes from light pink to dark pink (from pH ~6.0, $a = 0.5$ to pH ~8.5, $a = 1.95$) which then persists up to pH ~11.0. Also, the pH vs a curve shows steep inflection at $a = 2.0$ (pH ~8.8). Thus, it is concluded that Pd(tr)₂²⁻ is a dark pink complex. The colour of the corresponding Cd^{II}-tr mixture is comparable to that of tr in the entire range of experimental pH. However, a steep inflection in the pH vs a curve at $a = 2.0$ indicates the formation of Cd(tr)₂²⁻ complex. Beyond $a = 2.0$ association of hydroxyl ion with Cd(tr)₂²⁻ is evident from the titration curve. The pH vs a curve for 1 : 2, Pd²⁺-tr mixture shows a very steep inflection at $a = 2.0$ indicating the formation of Pd(tr)₂⁶⁻. Its formation is also supported by presence of light pink colour with increasing intensity from pH ~6.0 to 10.0 ($a = 2.0$). The complex equilibrium involving the formation of Cd(tr)₂⁶⁻ is also indicated by the pH vs a curve of the system, which shows a very strong inflection at $a = 2.0$.

The titration data of 1 : 1, Pd^{II}-ap mixture on comparing with that of ap indicates that metal-ligand association does not occur under the experimental conditions. The chelating tendency of Cd^{II} is also very weak. 1 : 1, Cd(ap)⁺ species exists below $a = 1.0$ (pH ~10.2). Its colour is almost similar to that of the ligand. Beyond pH ~10.2 formation of a dark yellow precipitate (probably due to neutral Cd(ap)(OH) complex) did not allow calculations. Colour of 1 : 2, Cd^{II}-ap mixture is also almost similar to that of ap itself in the entire range of pH. However, comparison of the titration curves of ap, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2, Cd^{II}-ap mixtures indicates the existence of complex equilibrium involving the formation of Cd(ap)₂.

The colour change in 1 : 1, metal (Pd^{II} or Cd^{II})-nn titration is almost similar to that in nn titration. But, the comparison of pH vs a curves of ligand and the complex systems indicate the formation of Pd(nn) and Cd(nn). In addition,

the titration curve for Pd^{II}-nn system shows a steep inflection at $a = 1.1$ in support of Pd(nn) formation. Beyond $a = 1.0$ interaction of OH⁻ ion takes place resulting in the formation of Pd(nn)(OH)⁻ and Cd(nn)(OH)⁻, Cd(nn)(OH)₂²⁻ in the corresponding metal-ligand systems. The colour changes in the 1 : 2, metal (Pd^{II} or Cd^{II})-nn mixture can be compared with those in nn or 1 : 1, metal (Pd^{II} or Cd^{II})-nn mixture. But, a steep inflection in the pH vs a curves at $a = 1.0$ in each system clearly supports the existence of Pd(nn)₂²⁻ or Cd(nn)₂²⁻ in their respective mixtures. In Cd^{II} system turbidity formation was noted beyond $a = 1.0$.

Simultaneous formation, of Pd(an)⁻ and Pd(an)(OH)₂²⁻ is evident from the pH vs a curve of 1 : 1, Pd^{II}-an mixture, which shows very steep inflection at $a = 2.0$. The titration curve further shows another steep inflection at $a = 3.0$. Hence, the second OH⁻ ion gets attached with the monohydroxo complex in an independent step. But, in case of Cd^{II}-an system the Cd(an)⁻ is formed independently as indicated by a steep inflection at $a = 1.0$ in the corresponding pH vs a curve. The 1 : 1, Cd^{II}-an mixture turns turbid beyond pH ~9.8. The colour changes in the complex titration mixtures are almost similar to those in an. Inflection at $a = 1.0$ in the pH vs a curve for 1 : 2, Pd^{II}- or Cd^{II}-an system indicates the formation of 1 : 2, metal-ligand complex species. Besides, Cd(an)₄⁴⁻ is coordinated to OH⁻ ion between $a = 1.0$ and 1.5. The colour change in each system is identical, and is also comparable to that in the ligand or 1 : 1, metal-ligand systems.

The equilibrium constant K_1 is greater than K_2 in each system. Table 1 shows that the chelating tendency of Pd^{II} > Cd^{II} with each ligand, except ca where the order is reversed. Further, a comparison of the equilibrium constants of Pd^{II}, Cd^{II} complexes (Table 1) and the earlier reported² Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes shows that the metal ions follow the under mentioned complexing tendency order :

- (i) Pd^{II} > Cd^{II} (tr system)
- (ii) Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Cd^{II} > Pd^{II} (ca system)
- (iii) Pd^{II} ~ Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} ~ Cd^{II} (nn system)
- (iv) Pd^{II} > Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II} (an system)

The higher values of equilibrium constant for Pd^{II}-an or Pd^{II}-nn complex than the corresponding Cu^{II} complex is inconsistent with the earlier reported work on these metal ions with other mixed nitrogen-oxygen^{1,5} donors. A reverse trend Cd^{II} > Pd^{II} as in ca system has also been observed^{3,6}. Earlier reported Cd^{II} complexes indicate its chelating tendency very close to that of Ni^{II} or Zn^{II} ions. The stability constant value depends upon the nature of ligand involved in the reaction⁷. In a majority of systems⁸ the most common ob-

Table 1. Equilibrium constants of binary, hydroxo and ternary complexes of Pd^{II} and Cd^{II} (25°, μ = 0.01 M KNO₃)

Reaction	log <i>k</i>	
	Pd ^{II}	Cd ^{II}
M ²⁺ + ca ²⁻ = M(ca)	7.43 ± 0.05	7.64 ± 0.02
M(ca) + ca ²⁻ = M(ca) ₂ ²⁻	6.14 ± 0.03	6.37 ± 0.03
M(ca) + OH ⁻ = M(ca)OH ⁻	3.74 ± 0.06	-
M ²⁺ + tr ⁴⁻ = M(tr) ²⁻	8.62 ± 0.02	8.39 ± 0.01
M(tr) ²⁻ + tr ⁴⁻ = M(tr) ₂ ⁶⁻	7.46 ± 0.07	7.23 ± 0.03
M ²⁺ + nn ²⁻ = M(nn)	5.32 ± 0.04	3.85 ± 0.05
M(nn) + nn ²⁻ = M(nn) ₂ ²⁻	4.41 ± 0.01	3.65 ± 0.01
M(nn) + OH ⁻ = M(nn)(OH) ⁻	3.35 ± 0.02	5.08 ± 0.02
M(nn)(OH) ⁻ + OH ⁻ = M(nn)(OH) ₂ ²⁻	-	3.64 ± 0.02
M ²⁺ + an ³⁻ = M(an) ⁻	9.03 ± 0.04	7.23 ± 0.01
M(an) ⁻ + an ³⁻ = M(an) ₂ ⁴⁻	9.01 ± 0.08	5.04 ± 0.04
M(an) ⁻ + OH ⁻ = M(an)(OH) ²⁻	10.05 ± 0.03	4.87 ± 0.06
M(an)(OH) ²⁻ + OH ⁻ = M(an)(OH) ₂ ³⁻	4.87 ± 0.01	-
M(an) ₂ ⁴⁻ + OH ⁻ = M(an) ₂ (OH) ⁵⁻	-	4.82 ± 0.05
M ²⁺ + ap ⁻ = M(ap) ⁺	-	4.14 ± 0.04
M(ap) ⁺ + ap ⁻ = M(ap) ₂	-	4.13 ± 0.05
M ²⁺ + ca ²⁻ + tr ⁴⁻ = M(ca)(tr) ⁴⁻	17.30 ± 0.09	16.85 ± 0.10
M ²⁺ + ca ²⁻ + nn ²⁻ = M(ca)(nn) ²⁻	13.00 ± 0.07	11.72 ± 0.06
M ²⁺ + ca ²⁻ + an ³⁻ = M(ca)(an) ³⁻	16.66 ± 0.02	14.95 ± 0.03
M ²⁺ + tr ⁴⁻ + nn ²⁻ = M(tr)(nn) ⁴⁻	14.16 ± 0.12	12.49 ± 0.10
M ²⁺ + tr ⁴⁻ + an ³⁻ = M(tr)(an) ⁵⁻	17.86 ± 0.06	15.80 ± 0.08
M(an)(OH) ²⁻ + nn ²⁻ = M(an)(OH)(nn) ⁴⁻	5.53 ± 0.05	-
M ²⁺ + ca ²⁻ + ap ⁻ = M(ca)(ap) ⁻	-	12.02 ± 0.08
M ²⁺ + ca ²⁻ + nn ²⁻ = M(ca)(nn) ²⁻	13.00 ± 0.07	11.72 ± 0.06
M ²⁺ + ca ²⁻ + an ³⁻ = M(ca)(an) ³⁻	16.66 ± 0.03	14.95 ± 0.03
M ²⁺ + tr ⁴⁻ + ap ⁻ = M(tr)(ap) ³⁻	-	12.72 ± 0.08
M ²⁺ + ap ⁻ + nn ²⁻ = M(ap)(nn) ⁻	-	8.24 ± 0.07
M ²⁺ + ap ⁻ + an ³⁻ = M(ap)(an) ²⁻	-	11.57 ± 0.03
M ²⁺ + nn ²⁻ + an ³⁻ = M(nn)(an) ³⁻	-	11.23 ± 0.05
M(nn)(an) ³⁻ + OH ⁻ = M(nn)(an)(OH) ⁴⁻	-	3.19 ± 0.02

served trend is Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II}.

Table 1 shows that the complexing tendency of different ligands with Cd^{II} follows the same order (tr > ca > an > ap > nn) as described earlier² for Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} complexes. But, in case of Pd^{II} systems the order is slightly changed to an > tr > ca > nn. Greater affinities for an than tr or ca is due to its preference to oxygen-nitrogen donors.

Coordination of OH⁻ ions with 1 : 1, Cd^{II}-ligand complexes follow the order : Cd (nn) > Cd (an)⁻ > Cd (tr)²⁻. It indicates that electron donation by OH⁻ ion is enhanced in the complexes where electron density around the central atom is lower, as described earlier for Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}

complexes². A parallel trend is observed in association of OH⁻ with metal (Pd or Cd)-nn complex : Pd (nn) < Cd (nn). But, a reverse trend is noted in metal-an complex system i.e. Pd (an)⁻ > Cd (an)⁻.

Ternary complexes : The 1 : 1 : 1 mixtures of Pd^{II} with pair of ligands ca-tr, ca-nn, ca-an, tr-nn, tr-an and nn-an or the similar mixtures of Cd^{II} consisting all possible pair of ligands ca, tr, ap, nn and an, remain in clear solution in the entire pH range of titration. None of the reaction mixtures shows any specific colour change during the titration. But, the presence of mixed ligand complex is inferred by comparing the titration curves of the ligands, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2,

metal-ligand and mixed ligand systems. Inflections in ternary titration curves in many systems are in additional support to the formation of the ternary complex. The Pd^{II} systems with pair of ligand ca-ap, tr-ap, nn-ap or an-ap could not be studied as the ligand ap does not coordinate with Pd^{II} under the present experimental conditions.

Experimental

$5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ solutions of Cd(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (B.D.H.) and PdCl₂ (C.D.H.) were prepared by dissolving the corresponding compounds. The content of Cd^{II} was determined by EDTA titration method. Pd^{II} was estimated gravimetrically using dimethylglyoxime as precipitating reagent⁹. Aqueous solutions of ca (B.D.H.), tr (Loba, G.R.) and an (disodium salt, C.D.H.) were prepared by direct weighing. Compounds nn and ap were purified by dissolving in aqueous alkali medium and then reprecipitating by dilute hydrochloric acid. Monosodium salt solution of nn was obtained by adding required alkali solution and ap was dissolved in known amount of alkali. The volume was raised to get $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentration of each ligand. The excess of alkali present in titration system of ap was neutralized by adding known amount of nitric acid solution before titration. Stock solutions of 0.1770 N NaOH, 0.02159 N HNO₃ and 1.0 M KNO₃ were prepared using A.R. grade chemicals.

The reaction mixtures prepared as described earlier² were titrated pH-metrically at 25° and at an ionic strength of 0.10 M KNO₃. The titration curves plotted between pH

and *a* values were used to analyse the existing equilibria and to evaluate the corresponding equilibrium constants.

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